

STATUS:

The virtual machine contains our complete toolchain for conducting variability-aware analysis, including the desugared source code and factbases for our five subject SPLs, the executable of variability-aware Rex, all our 10 analyses of interests expressed in Neo4j's input language, and the source code of lifted Neo4j. Additionally, the Neo4j databases for our five subject SPLs have already been set up to facilitate running queries within the databases. Our virtual machine is publicly available on Zenodo. Based on these reasons, we claim our artifacts meet the criteria of **Functional**, **Reusable**, and **Available**.